

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

Deliverable n°:	D2.1
Deliverable name:	Project website and social network profiles
Version:	1.0
Release date:	16/03/2017
Dissemination level:	Public
Status:	Submitted
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Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
0.1	03/03/2017	First draft version	Mette Magnussen
0.2	13/03/2017	Second draft version	Mette Magnussen
0.3	16/03/2017	Third draft version	Pol Olivella-Rosell
0.4	19/03/2017	Fourth draft version	Mette Magnussen
0.5	20/03/2017	Fifth draft version	Heidi Tuiskula, Mette Magnussen
1.0	20/03/2017	Final peer reviewed version	Santi Martinez Cristóbal Cordobés

Peer reviewed by:

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Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
All

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Executive summary

Communication and dissemination activities will serve as vital parts of the INVADE project, both to create awareness and common knowledge about the project and to promote and spread results and outcomes. The website will have the URL www.h2020invade.eu and serves as a news and information hub for the upcoming dissemination and communication tasks throughout the project period.

WordPress functions as the recommended Content Management System (CMS) for the project website, which is an open source, license free CMS with flexible templates, various editorial functionalities and marginal maintenance costs.

The structure of the INVADE website will be easy to navigate, providing the visitor information about the project and partners, recent news, deliverables and upcoming events. Social media accounts will be integrated on the website as feeds, thus functioning as an effective way of keeping the website updated. INVADE will have profiles on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.

Bridging the gap between INVADE website and associated social media profiles will be essential for the communication and dissemination part of the project. Obtaining a good content management strategy, hence a content plan for managing, optimizing and evaluating the ongoing activities will be important in order to keep up timeliness and structure.

Content and inbound marketing are well known marketing methods which enables the creation of professional and engaging content towards important stakeholders of the project. Combining these methods with a structured and well-organized content plan will set the foundation for a successful implementation of the communication and dissemination activities. In addition to written content, one large branding film will be produced, explaining the scope of the project, amongst several minor films which will serve as smaller status updates for social media.

The website and social media profiles will be organized and managed by WP2, and in this matter ensuring an efficient and flexible structure throughout the project period. Results and outcomes from the activities will be closely analysed, thus optimized in order to strive for high performance within the communication and dissemination tasks.

1 Introduction

A consortium of 12 European partners has won one of the largest European research and innovation projects ever in the field of Smart Grid & Storage. The new Horizon 2020 EU project, INVADE, will deliver and validate through large-scale pilots a cloud-based flexibility management system integrated with EVs and battery storages at mobile, distributed and centralized levels. The goal of the project is to change the way energy is used, stored and generated by utilizing renewable energy more effectively, optimizing the supply of electricity and making services more end-user-centric.

This document is INVADE project deliverable D2.1, “Project website and social network profiles”, which corresponds to task T2.2 “Digital media”. The main purpose of D2.1 is to present the technical and editorial description of the INVADE website. Document describes the purpose of the site, the different templates for landing pages, the structure and functionality of the site, maintenance of the site, and how the overall communication and dissemination tasks are optimized by analysing and evaluating the ongoing results.

Further we will define the INVADE social media platforms and accounts and describe how to bridge the gap between the channels in order to deliver well planned and structured quality content for the projects various stakeholders.

Consequently, this document will describe the content management process and plan, the creation of both written and visual content for the website and for the social media accounts.

2 Communication and dissemination

Communication and dissemination activities are one of the core activities for the project implementation and a successful deployment of its outcome after the project lifetime. Through communication and dissemination activities consortium can create general awareness of the project to wide range of audience, present results and create potential for exploitation of developed INVADE solution both inside the consortium and in wider scale throughout Europe and beyond.

Communication and dissemination activities are based on two pillars:

Pillar I – Awareness-oriented pillar to create awareness and a common knowledge about the project and its key findings among identified stakeholders and citizens at large.

The pillar also includes preparation of dissemination and communication material targeting wider audiences – project website, flyers and posters, professional video production, organisation of two larger scale project events and other activities aiming to reach the public in general.

Increasing awareness of the project «Spread the word»: In practice, this pillar includes using traditional and social marketing channels to make the project and its purpose known among the stakeholders by promotion through articles and films on the INVADE website. Search engine optimization is used in order to achieve good ranking on Google organic hits. This will be vital for achieving increased traffic to the website. To achieve good ranking, it is important to optimize each article and post with relevant keywords in headings, body text, images, relevant links with keywords and to have a good format which is in accordance to Google's algorithms. In addition, Facebook ads with tools like target audiences are used in order to be more likely to attract the right target group in a more cost effective manner. Other promotion in social media will be to have regular posts and status updates on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn. Active use relevant hash tags in Twitter context.

Pillar II – Results-oriented pillar to disseminate and communicate the results during the project execution. This pillar is focused on activities that could make a difference in how the Integrated INVADE Platform is designed and delivered to the market. During the activities of this pillar, the consortium creates sustainable and trusted relationships and communication with the relevant stakeholder communities – research, academia, public and industry- addressing all interlinked sectors: Renewable energy, transport, information and communication technologies and social sciences. In addition to activities related to project website and social media profiles, this pillar includes for example arranging several workshops, meetings and publishing project results through different publications, both scientific and those directed towards a wider audience.

Storytelling, documentation and spreading of news: In this phase, content marketing is used as marketing method and the INVADE website is used as a hub to disseminate news from the project, current status and "discovery" of activities, and to inform about the results and effects. We will at this stage use both the traditional newsletter and frequently blog articles where the recipient can choose the desired update frequency and topics for updates. Use of social media is central in this stage as well, and works well with updates and information which needs to be communicated in a quick and effective way. As an example, through twitter we can deliver daily glimpses of researchers' everyday work, create attention to our meetings, workshops and other events and

establish communication with other projects, researchers and general audience interested in our project whereas through Facebook and project website we can deliver longer posts and tell the core story about the large-scale pilots throughout their lifetime.

Aim for all communication and dissemination activities is to create an interesting story of the INVADE project, which attracts all stakeholders from European citizens to scientists, industry and decision makers. This is necessary to support the projects goals to 1) have significant impact on society and all stakeholders involved, to 2) create a long-term lasting link between the project beneficiaries and the stakeholders and to 3) ensure that the integrated INVADE solution would be exploitable in the European Economic Area and beyond.

3 What the website should be

The website will be available with URL www.h2020invade.eu and will serve as the main news and information hub for the upcoming dissemination and communication activities throughout the INVADE projects lifetime of 3 years. The website should present challenges and objectives of the project, introduce the project beneficiaries, and present key outcomes in a form of reports, presentations, films, articles, films, press reports (media attention) and social media posts and tweets. The website will be a key tool in order to raise a common understanding of the project and will target the projects different stakeholders in an effective matter. In the post project years the webpage will function as a digital summary and show case of the project scope, goals, deliveries, outcomes, results, effects and impact.

The website should be frequently updated with new content from the consortium, to both keep the site relevant and to trigger interest of the different INVADE stakeholders.

4 Creating the website

The description of developing the website constitutes two main areas: The front end technical description, which presents the overall structure and node tree of the website and the connected templates for the different landing pages. Both main/parent nodes and sub/child nodes will be included in the presentation. The back end technical description describes the technical functionalities and options, which should be available.

The editorial description suggests different tool options the editors of the webpage should have access to in order to fulfil the given communication tasks.

The INVADE website will be created in English at the beginning of the project period, but will, later on, have connected, similar, twin websites in other languages which applies to the different nationalities of the consortium.

The first, basic version of the INVADE website will be delivered on March 31st 2017.

4.1.1 Preferred Content Management System (CMS)

The new and final INVADE website will be developed in WordPress, which is a licence-free, open-source content management system (CMS). The CMS platform is based on PHP and MySQL and provides both developer and editor a large scale of flexibility when it comes to both creating the website and maintaining it. WordPress provides sites with responsive web design, hence the www.h2020invade.eu site will be equally functional on regular desktop, tablets and mobile devices.

WordPress distinguishes between “Page” and “Post”, whereas “Pages” will be the different landing pages (nodes) on the site. These tend to be more static and obtains attributes that differs from “Posts”, which are all news, blogs, articles and other status updates, that are continuously produced for the website.

4.2 Front end description

The term “front end” describes in this context the interactive and structural layout of the website. This chapter explains the overall, visible structure of the website with wireframes for each webpage, illustrating the layout.

4.2.1 Structure / content on the INVADE website

The structure of the website, presented in the figure below, shows the various pages and headings with explanations in the subsequent paragraphs. The website will target both visitors in need of a deeper understanding of the project as well as the visitors who want a simple overview of the project.

There is a need for different levels of dissemination and communication provided through the website. Some stakeholders visit the website looking for deep understanding of the project details where as some look for brief overview. As the overall goal for the dissemination and communication activities is to create an impact in the society, project

takes great care on developing material understandable for all citizens, not only for scientific community. As an example, a populist summary of the project, will be developed and presented on the front page connected to the top images or film.

The mega drop down menu (MDDM) will be static and always visible at the top of the website. WordPress allows the editor to change and manage the MDDM if needed.

- The Front page: Provides an appellative summary of the project and presents the latest news and updates.
- The Project: Describes the project in more detail and technical terms.
- Deliverables: Provides a structured plan of the project process
- Events: Presents an overview over the upcoming events with information regarding date, place and subject.
- Partners: Introduces the project partners and their role in the project
- Contact: Includes a form for requests or feedback to the project.
- Generic article page: The template for articles and news
- News / Press: Contains press releases and news about the project. A download site for files, PDF's, press releases and general news.

INDEX

4.2.2 Front page

The front page serves as the first attention puller of the INVADE project. A large image or illustration will be presented on the site, which is related to the essence and scope of the project. This should be able to give the visitor a hint of the uniqueness of the project and trigger to read more about the project in the additional pages and posts. Later, the image or illustration can be replaced with a professional branding film covering the core value of the project.

Further, the front page should provide the visitor with a short project summary, which will link to landing page explaining the project and its vision in a detailed matter.

The social media feed is strategic placed at the left side of the page, contributing to obtaining the sense of a non-static website. The feed will also include the newest produce posts / articles from the various consortium partners of the project.

The logos of the consortium partners will be visible at the bottom of the page, where the link will lead the visitor to another internal landing page describing the partner's role in the project. We do not link to the partners own homepage at this stage, since the goal of the front page is to trigger the visitor to read more about the project on this website and consequently increasing the understanding of the project.

In summary, the front page's sole task is to function as a trigger point and portal for the rest of the website, simultaneously providing the stakeholders of the project with the latest updated news.

FRONT PAGE

4.2.3 The project

This page will present the INVADE project with a brief summary that captures the essence of the project. Further, there will be information about the project scope, the technical description and implementation, expected results and impact for the environment, the market and the effects on a socio-economic level.

THE PROJECT

On the project site there will also be a box that allows the visitors to enter the Pilot Site page. The Pilot Site page contains boxes from each pilot site. The box contains a picture and a “read more” function. When clicking on the desired Pilot Site, it will direct the visitors to an article page with the latest updated information from this Pilot Site

PILOT SITES

TOP MENU The project Deliverables Events Partners Contact News/press

SPAIN Read more ...	NORWAY Read more ...	BULGARIA Read more ...
GERMANY Read more ...	THE NETHERLANDS Read more ...	

ARTICLE PAGE - PILOT SITE

TOP MENU The project Deliverables Events Partners Contact News/press

PICTURE PILOT SITE

PILOT SITE INFORMATION	Contact info
------------------------	--------------

4.2.4 Events

The Events page contains a generic events top picture. The coming events will be categorized by an “event” box for each happening. The box contains a picture and a short summary of the event. The event boxes will be categorized by dates, with the next event first. For a more detailed information of the event, it is possible to click the “Read more”-link and this will take the visitor to an events article page.

4.2.5 Partners

Each of the partners in the project will be presented with a boxed logo and an option with a roll-down bar that extracts and show a short information about the company and their role in the project. It will also show a link to a new page (article page, partner) where the visitor can read more about the specific partner, their role in the INVADE project, their work packages and information about the key resources and contact persons. The page will contain a link to the company web site as well. The members of the consortium will be encouraged to link their own web site to the project web site and vice versa to make it a hub according to the way Google defines it. This will be partly instrumental in boosting

the page ranking done by the search engine.

PARTNERS

TOP MENU

LOGO Dropdown company info ▼	LOGO ▼	LOGO ▼
LOGO Company text ▲	LOGO ▼	LOGO ▼

ARTICLE PAGE - PARTNER

TOP MENU

PICTURE COMPANY

PARTNER ROLE IN PROJECT	Contact info Link to company website
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4.2.6 Deliverables

The deliverables section has an overview over the different milestones and work packages presented in the project with always the next touchpoint first. Each touchpoint will be presented with a picture and the content for each section.

For a more visualized overview of the project there will also be a graphic timeline presented on the page. The timeline should be interactive, and the visitors can at any point click on the "Timeline tree", which will automatically bring the visitors to the section with the content of interest.

Articles and reports connected to the specific sections will be possible under each section as well as under "The project" and "press" section.

DELIVERABLES

4.2.7 News and press

The news and press site contains a newsfeed, SOME-feed, Press releases, downloads and contact. Here we intend to create a flexible interplay between our social media accounts and the web site. Twitter allows only brief messages, but is easy to use. The media triggers fast growth of followers. Press releases that are posted in the press / news section will be announced with a link on Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook. It is

reasonably well established that brief news with a link to more substantial information are more often retweeted, bookmarked and commented than mere retweets and brief announcements without more substantial information support. In addition to references to important responses in the social media, we will continuously monitor the web, and with the aid of the project members, track down references to our project found in general media locally and world-wide. Such references will briefly be commented on as part of the publication process.

NEWS / PRESS

TOP MENU		
NEWSFEED	PRESS RELEASES	SOME-FEED
<p>Heading</p> <p>Pic. Text</p> <hr/> <hr/> <hr/>		
DOWNLOADS	CONTACT	
<p>Article</p> <p>PDF</p> <p>File</p>		

4.2.8 Contact

This part contains a form where people can make contact with relevant key holders of the project. This will be made with simple and intuitive boxes to fill in questions, feedback, requests or to just make contact. The project will regularly issue announcements through social media and invite followers to join the network. The contact form will also be a tool where we invite the Network of Interest and followers on social media to contribute ideas and tentative solutions with the project in a structured fashion without having to share such input openly on social media.

CONTACT

TOP MENU	
CONTACT INFO SMART INN. NORWAY	Contact form
CONTACT INFO FOR THE PRESS	

Access to the Technical advisory group an exploitation group is via a dropdown menu when hovering the «Contact» button in the top menu. The two sites are quite similar. It has an explanatory text about the group on top, and follows up with a picture of each member in its respective group and a short summary about the person.

TECHNICAL ADVISORY GROUP

TOP MENU The project Deliverables Events Partners Contact News/press

INTRO TEXT ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY GROUP

Picture	Picture	Picture	Picture	Picture
Short summary of person and contact info				
=====	=====	=====	=====	=====
Picture	Picture	Picture	Picture	Picture

EXPLOITATION GROUP

4.2.9 Article page - generic

This article page will serve as an ordinary page for news articles, press releases, publications and other stories. The functionality will include the possibility to have links for YouTube-films, pictures, links, documents, publications and regular text.

4.2.10 Generic framework

The framework of the site could be structured like this:

- Desktop: 5 column grid, whereas four of the columns are content related and the fifth column is add-ons. Each column could be 200 px wide with 30 px margin.
- Tablet: 4 columns wide. Each columns could be 170 px wide with 20 px margin
- Mobil: 1 column wide.

Each page or post should include the following attributes:

- Social media likes and follow options
- Links to related pages or posts

- Date and author for the post (not relevant for the static pages)
- Option for newsletter subscription

4.3 Back end description

The back end user interface should be flexible and provide the editor with sufficient Wordpress tools for structuring the website. The paragraph regarding the technical options describes the settings for the page and posts in the purpose of having a good site structure / navigation, SEO and overall frame work. The editorial options defines the options for editing the content of the page or post.

4.3.1 Technical options

The backend tool should provide the editor with the following options:

- Edit existing url for a landing page or post and provide a short-url for communications purposes. Example www.h2020invade.eu/about-the-project. Short url for the same page: www.h2020invade.eu/project
- Access the version history for both pages and posts, hence being able to publish older versions of the post or page.
- Edit the node levels for the pages: Parent node and child node. When structuring a new website it is utterly important to have a clear plan for the overall node tree (pages) and navigation. Each main page should be tagged as the parent node and the following sub-pages as child nodes. For example, in this case the “Contact” page would serve as the parent node and the linked child node would be “technical advisory board” and exploitation group”. When we tag the sites with proper node level, this affects the url of the page and the node structure:
 - With proper node tags: www.h2020invade.eu/contact/technical-advisory-board and www.h2020invade.eu/contact/exploitation-group
 - Without proper node tags: www.h2020invade.eu/technical-advisory-board and www.h2020invade.eu/exploitation-group
- Hide and show the breadcrumb for each page or post (the node tree level)
- Specify whether the page should be hidden from search (internal page search or / and search engines)

- Edit the mega drop down menu (MDDM): Ability to change name, node level, url, etc.
- Edit social plugins: Link to Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn pages. Ability to edit the image for the specific post.
- Add and edit SEO (search engine optimization) settings for the page and posts with the following options: MetaDescriptionTag, MetaKeywordsTag, Meta Robot Stag / ScriptTag, NoScript tag and Pixel Container.
- Add and edit key words for each page or post. These keywords will contribute to a good SEO foundation and will serve as searchable tags on the website. In this way, the visitor of the website will be able to find relevant posts or pages.
- Possibility to have multiple languages.
- Create users and administrators with different access levels.

4.3.2 Editorial options

The editorial options should be a selection of common “windows office word” functionality, such as options to:

- Choose H1 to H6 headline and have the text in bold, italic, underscored or in bullet points.
- Add links in the text area of the post or page. Internal link opens the page in the same pane/window of the browser, external link opens the page in a new pane/window.
- Add documents (PDF, Excel sheets, word, image files, etc). Internal documents opens the document in the same pane/window of the browser, external link opens the page in a new pane/window.
- Edit, add or change main image, image carousel or video.
- Choose colours for the font from the INVADE graphic guidelines.
- Add videos from YouTube/Vimeo in the content section
- Add iFrame in the content section. This could be useful for showing the location of pilot sites or location for events by using Google Maps, etc.
- Add author for the post and have the option of hiding or showing this information on the page.

- Set the date of publication; either back in time or for planning a publication to come. The date should be visible on posts, not pages.

5 Social media network profiles

The INVADE project will have a presence on selected social network communities, which will play an important part of the overall communication and dissemination work. The profiles will be integrated on the website as feeds, thus functioning as an effective way of keeping the website updated.

This document will define purpose, content and structure of the INVADE social media profiles on the following platforms: Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn. The accounts will be integrated into the project website (feed).

The social media accounts will be vital in maintaining the interests of different stakeholders throughout the project and in the post project period. The key objective will be to outreach citizens as well as different stakeholder groups about the Integrated INVADE Platform and its potential. The social networks will, in correlations with the website, also be used to collect feedback and extract information from vital stakeholders, in order to utilize and improve the INVADE platform and its business and exploitation plan.

Managing the social media accounts will be handled in the overall content plan, which will include information about topic / issue, preferred channel/account, information about the audience, the desired result (information, knowledge- or competence, etc.), the choice of photo or film, when the post will be published and the responsible person for the publication.

- The INVADE Twitter account has been created with the URL <https://twitter.com/INVADEH2020>), and will be used during the project lifetime. Twitter will cover ongoing news and updates from the consortium partners, and for collecting input and information during and after large-scale INVADE events. In terms of the INVADE workshops, the channel will be used for involving relevant stakeholders and to address the different workshop topics in an effective matter. Twitter discussions will link to different themes and will provide an opportunity for the stakeholder to be involved directly with live discussions during a workshop or event. WP2 will encourage the consortium members and other partners to

actively use @INVADEH2020 when suitable. However, the content plan will ensure a regular frequency of at least 5 tweets a week.

- The INVADE Facebook account, <https://www.facebook.com/invadeh2020> has been created. The presence in this social media channel is to target the communication towards the younger generation, such as students, and towards various national and local associations and communities promoting a sustainable way of living. Consequently, Facebook will require an appealing and rather sophisticated visual presentation of the project information because of the overload of information and advertisement in the feeds. It is vital to obtain a plan concerning target audiences and how to reach and attract them. Regular updates of 2-4 Facebook posts a week, will be ensured by WP2 and managed through the content plan.
- LinkedIn is considered a network targeting stakeholders of the European industry, initiatives and associations focusing on renewable energy storage, the smart grid, and novel ICT solutions for the energy sector. The channel will function as a trigger for different stakeholders (e.g. electric vehicles' owners). The overall LinkedIn activity will be managed and controlled by WP2, consequently by following the recommended update frequency described in the content plan. Approximately 2-4 posts per week.

6 Content management

The overall communication and dissemination plan will include an overview of the entire period with all planned activities, channels, target groups and dates. Hence a description of everything that will be disseminated and communicated during the different work packages and stages of the project. This will include information about of the market which will be penetrated, detailed description of the main objectives and KPIs, which audiences to attract and which to excluded, which channels to be used, the selection of messages to the various target groups in the different channels, design and customization of material, responsible editors, ongoing evaluation of results and impact, plan for internal communication within the consortium, coordination with internal and external parties, timeline with milestones for the different phases, plan for evaluation and measurements (tools) and report frequency.

6.1 Content plan

Bridging the gap between the website and the social media accounts will be essential for the communication and dissemination part of the INVADE project. This will be done by obtaining a good content management strategy, which ensures the content to be optimized and spread through the right digital channels to the right target group and to the right time. Having a content plan for managing this will be important in order to keep up timeliness and structure.

The plan will display a timeline for the entire 3-year project period where the responsible editor and coordinator will use Excel as a tool for managing the plan, thus being a working document. The articles, news, posts and tweets should always be settled for a 2 months period in advance, allowing ad hoc status updates to compliment the plan.

The content will reflect the projects work tasks and the plan will be created in accordance to the expected activities, events and happenings.

Below is an illustration of an excel worksheet that includes the upcoming content for the website and social media accounts. The plan presents the following information:

- Publishing date
- Status of the article/post/tweet: Draft, finished or published
- Type of content: Information, status update, branding, entertaining, etc.
- Which work package or project phase the content is related to.
- Information about the author: The responsible partner for creating the content and providing it to the editor of the website. Both name of the company and the name of the contact person should be included in the plan.
- Small thumbnail picture of the image: A good way of identifying the post, controlling the workflow, thus ensuring that the right content is being published at the right time and in the right channels.
- Link to image or film, and information about where to find it. Information about the image rights should also be included here.
- Text for Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn in separate columns
- Word count for Twitter
- Responsible editor to publish the particular content
- Comments, if any.

In an extended version of the content plan, one can also include the results for the post (number of likes, retweets, shares, comments, visitors, etc.).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	
1	Content plan - INVADE										
2											
3											
4	Date	Status	Type	Work package /delivery	Author / Responsible partner and contact person for providing content	Image	Image URL / rights	URL for web site article / blog post / publication	Text for Facebook	Text for Twitter	Text for LinkedIn
5	01.08.17	Draft, finished, published	Information		E.g. Mette Magnussen, SMARTIO			www.h2020invade.eu/about	Smart system of renewable energy storage based on INtegrated EVs and bAtteries to empower mobile, Distributed and centralised Energy storage in the distribution grid	Smart system of renewable energy	Smart system of renewable energy storage INtegrated E to empower Distributed i Energy storage distribution
6	02.08.2017	Draft, finished, published	Branding					www.h2020invade.eu/about	Smart system of renewable energy storage based on INtegrated EVs and bAtteries to empower mobile, Distributed and centralised Energy storage in the distribution grid	Smart system of renewable energy	Smart system of renewable energy storage INtegrated E to empower Distributed i Energy storage distribution
7	03.08.17	Draft, finished, published	Status update					www.h2020invade.eu/about	Smart system of renewable energy storage based on INtegrated EVs and bAtteries to empower mobile, Distributed and centralised Energy storage in the distribution grid	Smart system of renewable energy	Smart system of renewable energy storage INtegrated E to empower Distributed i Energy storage distribution
	04.08.2017	Draft, finished, published	Information						Smart system of renewable energy storage based on INtegrated EVs and bAtteries	Smart system of renewable energy	Smart system of renewable energy storage INtegrated E

Example of a functional layout for a content plan for social media and web posts / articles.

Recommended frequency of spreading the planned content:

- Website articles, publications, news: 1-2 times a week
- Facebook posts: 2-4 times a week
- LinkedIn posts: 2-4 times a week
- Twitter updates: Min. 1 tweet a day.

6.2 Content and inbound marketing

The INVADE project will base its communication and marketing strategy on creating relevant, informal and engaging content for the stakeholder throughout the project period. The storytelling during the coming three years will be of severe importance in order to document the different stages of the project, the deliverables, the findings, the results, and the outcomes. The importance of showing the uniqueness of the project, thus documenting the impact the INVADE project will have on the electricity market, in terms of cost reduction, increased grid management efficiency and for the future business models, the everyday life of the end users and society, will be central in the overall communication and dissemination plan.

Creation of various content will be a task for the consortium partners as a whole, consequently providing the stakeholders with a broad spectre of news and updates from different parts of the project implementation.

Content and inbound marketing is marketing methodology that uses relevant content (both written and visual) to attracts target groups in order to increase the awareness level of the project, inform and explain the expected outcomes and results, document the ongoing activities and events and doing so in a flexible and good matter. In addition to storytelling and documentation, the goal of content and inbound marketing is to attract stakeholders and other visitors to subscribe to the project newsletter. Each produced article should refer or link to a form for newsletter subscription, thus ensuring a repeatedly and flexible matter of communicating to the project stakeholders.

6.3 Videos

Visualization is an important part of the INVADE project and the plan is to produce one professional video about the project and several minor “status videos” which will be contributed through the website news feed, press and news site and on the front page. Making the scope visual provides an opportunity to explain a rather complex and delicate project in a good and engaging way. Beneath is an illustration of the project which serves as a solid foundation for a film where traditional filming combined with graphic design can make an impressive, appellative and educational presentation of the overall project.

Illustration “Project Concept” from the INVADE proposal.

6.3.1 Video format and purpose

We will produce several videos during the project period, both branding related films and shorter films with the purpose of communicating news and findings.

- A professional and extended branding film of the project. This will explain the vision, scope and the goal of the project, focusing on challenges and expected outcomes, results, impact and effects.
- Shorter, viral videos: The purpose of these films is to briefly communicating news and stories of interest. These films will normally be published in social media as a status update with the goal of viral spread.

Using videos alongside traditional written content provides a good balance to the overall communication plan and will help spread our story in relevant social medias.

7 Managing and monitoring the website and social media accounts

WP2 will manage the website and the related social media accounts. The content plan will function as a key tool in order to organize, structure, produce and promote the planned content during the project period. Additional, WP2 is responsible for coordinating and monitor social media discussions, feedback and comments.

Further, the WP2 will monitor and analyse the ongoing activities and results, which will be presented in a regularly web statistics reports during the project period.

7.1 Statistics - monitoring the website and social media accounts

In order to be successful within communication and dissemination, it is essential being able to extract and understand the performance of the website and the social media platforms. Both the INVADE website and social media accounts will be continuously evaluated and optimized during the overall project period, to ensure achievement of desired outcomes or results. Hence, adjusting and testing content structure, messages, keywords and links, thus monitoring the following performance.

Obtaining a solid routine and process for monitoring and analyzing ongoing activities will influence further actions and plans for the communication. Analytical tools, such as Google Analytics (web analytics) and different social media analytics tools for insights

(Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), plays a vital part of measuring performance and results. Understanding not only the rationales behind negative results, but also being able to determine the cause of positive outcomes, are equally important in order to achieve future success in the communications process.

When creating the website www.h2020invade.eu, a Google Analytics account will be established in order to track the ongoing results from the planned activities. The agility between the website and the associated social media account will be closely observed and measured.

Google Analytics will serve as the key analytics tool for analysing the continuing communication and dissemination tasks. The analytics process will consist of the following measurements:

- Number of visits and clicks: Provides information about the total traffic and frequency of visits to the entire website.
- Bounce rate: Indicates how relevant the visitor finds the content of the site. It shows the percentage of visitors who enter the site and then leave ("bounce") instead of continuing to other pages within the same site.
- Source and medium: Provides information about the source of the traffic and which channels is more effective when it comes to duration of visit, bounce rate and number of pages visited.
- Geographic location, based on IP-address.

Other measurements:

- Page ranking on Google (and other search engines): Indicates the websites performance within relevant keywords on Google.
- Number of people signing up for INVADE Newsletters

Social media monitoring:

- Number of followers in INVADE social media accounts; Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn
- Number of actions in social media, such as comments, shares, likes, retweets. These results provides insight on how successful the communication is and what further actions needs to be made. Additionally this indicated how well the communication hits the various stakeholders and target group.

- Number of tweets, posts and comments where INVADE is mentioned by name or hashtags.

8 Conclusions

The INVADE website aims to function as an effective and appellative information and news hub during the projects lifetime. The main objective will be to communicate and interact with important stakeholders, citizens and partners in a professional and engaging matter. Providing them with well-written articles, scientific publications, updates about the ongoing activities, upcoming events and results from pilot sites. The project website and social media accounts will play a vital role in communicating and positioning the INVADE project amongst stakeholders. WP2 will manage and optimize the planning, execution and analysis tasks in accordance with the continuously evolvement of the project.

The first, basic version of the INVADE website will be delivered on March 31st 2017.

9 References

[1] Wordpress.org: <https://wordpress.org>